

NATURAL CONDITIONS AND RECREATIONAL OPPORTUNITIES OF THE WESTERN TIANSHAN MOUNTAINS

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Abstract: *This article is about the important peculiarities of improving ecological education in natural geography. Furthermore, different approaches and benefits of teaching environmental education were given.*

Key Words: *transboundary, cultivated, commercial, vertebrate biodiversity, transnational, glaciers, domesticated plants, visitor facilities.*

Western Tien-Shan is a transboundary and serial property situated in the highly mountainous areas spanning three Central Asian countries. The property is divided into seven protected areas that capture some of the most biodiverse components of an already species rich region. Western Tien-Shan is perhaps most famous for its populations of wild relatives to modern day commercial fruit trees, such as apricot and pear, but most notably for apple, which is thought to have originated in this region. The property also supports a large number of animal species, many of which are threatened, such as the snow leopard and saker falcon. The topographically dramatic landscape remains largely forested and acts as a key biodiversity reservoir for the region. Western Tien-Shan represents an exceptional diversity and beauty of a mosaic of landscapes, a unique combination of different types of ecosystems, outstanding diversity of fauna and flora with a considerable proportion of endemic species and communities, as well as a large number of rare and threatened species. It is among most species rich sites in the Pamir-Tien-Shan Highlands province and close to half of its species are endemic to Middle Asia. Western Tien-Shan has an exceptional value as a centre of origin of cultivated plants. It is home to a number of wild species related to domesticated fruit plants including wild apples, apricot, pistachio, vine, plum, pear, walnut and hawthorn.

The Western Tien-Shan supports outstanding diversity of plant and animal species with high level of endemism and many species of global

conservation importance. The vertebrate biodiversity found in the region of Western Tien Shan includes 61 species of mammals, 316 species of birds, 17 species of reptiles, 3 species of amphibians and more than 20 fish species, and almost all of these species are reported as occurring in the area of the property. Protected areas included in the property have adequate level of protection corresponding to IUCN categories Ia and II. Individual components of the property are sufficient to jointly maintain functioning of natural systems of Western Tien-Shan and fully represent the properties and processes that reflect their significance. The main pressures to the property are poaching, cattle grazing, illegal logging, haying, illegal harvesting of flowers etc. The typical kinds of natural disasters in the Western Tien-Shan are rock falls, landslides, mudslides, avalanches; droughts lead to fires in dry years. Some parts of the property are surrounded by highly populated areas and as result they have possibility for good number of visitors from one side and threat from uncontrolled recreation from other side. In all the protected areas these threats and pressures are taken into consideration in management plans and the staff is regularly trained for control and adequate reaction in case of disasters.

All components of the property are state protected areas of national importance and are protected under national legislations of Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan. Reserves have status of strictly protected natural areas, where any use of animals and plants and any economic activities are prohibited. Also, a very limited access of visitors, obligatory accompanied by protected areas inspectors and only in specially designated areas is allowed. Sayram-Ugam national park has areas with the same strictly protected regimes as in reserves, as well areas accessible for visitors and for strictly limited use of nature. All areas of Western Tien-Shan are properties of the government, each of them have its own administration and staff and they are managed by an authorised state executive bodies of each country with funding from the state budgets. The property as a whole will be managed by a transboundary Steering Committee (consisting of representatives of the protected areas and of responsible governmental bodies) with the main role for coordination of conservation and management efforts, exchange of experience and information. The Committee will be established shortly after inscription of Western Tien-Shan in the World Heritage List and will work as intergovernmental group with scheduled meetings (at least once a year) and teleconferences.

Western Tien-Shan is both a transnational and serial property that spans the Republics of Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan. The property is situated within the Tian-Shan Mountains, one of the seven largest mountain ranges on the planet, which spans 2,500 km and four countries. With the addition of the Altai Mountains to the north, Kunlun Mountains to the south and the Pamir Mountains to the west, the region covers significant topographical diversity. The property itself is predominantly located in a triangle between the Kyrgyzstan town of Sheker, the Uzbekistan capital of Tashkent and the Kazakhstan town of Shymkent. However, three of the component parts are considerably further north in Kazakhstan, closer to Kentau. The property's topography is characterised by high mountain tops that descend quickly into steep river valleys. The property is located at the junction of two geological formation zones: North Tian-Shan and Karatau-Naryn, with the Tian-Shan Mountains being considered the younger formation. The Tian-Shan Mountains are predominantly composed of Proterozoic crystalline gneisses and sedimentary rocks from the Paleozoic era. The soils of the property are clearly stratified by altitude, with 12 distinct soil types ranging from 'alpine common' at high altitudes to 'alluvial: forest meadow and meadow' in the pastures of the valleys. Springs, streams and rivers are all common throughout the property, with snowmelt from the higher peaks producing the greatest flows in spring.

Kazakhstan: Karatau is composed largely of rocky ridges and the Mynzhylki Massif, which start at 700 metres a.s.l and rise to just over 2,000 metres. The area has distinctly steep ravines which are interspersed with both seasonal and permanent streams. There are three main rivers in this part of the property: Baiyldyr, Khantagi and Biresik. Aksu-Jabagy, though still mountainous, does not extend above 2,800 metres, and has generally more gentle slopes than some other areas in the property. The area does have extensive rock exposure, with alluvial fans of rocks and moraine deposits, as well as multiple small lakes. Sairam-Ugam is mountainous, with the highest point, Sailam peak, reaching 4,238 metres a.s.l. Several ridges branch off from this point, creating steep 'v' shaped valleys throughout the property. A couple of glaciers are still present, with the largest being situated around Sailam Peak.

Kyrgyzstan: Sary-Chelek is situated in an alpine basin protected by three distinct ridges: Chatkal, Atoinok and Bozbu-Too, which rise up to around 4,000 metres. The area's main river, the Khodzha-Ata, is predominantly fed through melting snows and glaciers, which also feed several large lakes in the area, which can reach several hundred metres in

depth. Besh-Aral is surrounded by two ridges: Pskem and Chatkal. There are numerous scree slopes and intermontane troughs. The Chatkal River and its feeders function as the main waterway in the area. Padysha-Ata is characterised by high contrasts in its topography. The lower slopes of Padysha-Ata have low-lying alluvial cones, often covered by vegetation, and 'adysr' which resemble smooth undulations with blunted peaks. When moving up the valley, the adysr become larger. The Padysha-Ata River is interspersed with large boulders but remains a fast-flowing river.

Uzbekistan: Chatkal, like most other parts of the property, contains a multitude of steep slopes and small lakes. The area is particularly difficult to access despite the absence of glaciers.

The region has a distinctly continental climate, with cold and snowy winters followed by hot, dry summers. Because the region is very mountainous, the climate experiences notable zonality and microclimates. The coldest months for the property are between November and January, where temperatures can go as low as -38°C (Piedmont area) and snow can easily go above 1 metre in the medium-altitude mountains. Comparatively, the summer months can be very hot and reach maximums of 47°C (Karatau). Precipitation within the property falls mainly between February and June and varies widely in terms of altitude, with lower slopes in certain parts of the property receiving in the region of 100 mm and higher altitudes often receiving over 800 mm.

The property, and the region more broadly, are of high biological importance for the resident fruit forests, which contain 10 species of wild relatives to domesticated plants. The western Tien-Shan region is one of 12 centres globally for agrobiodiversity, containing 38 important crop species and 20% of the world's cereals, vegetable and spice plants (Dzhangaliev et al. 2003).

To sum up all above, [it is important to stress that](#) Ecotourism is listed as being an integral component of visitor facilities and management within the Kyrgyzstan components of the property. However, there are no stated visitor statistics for these component parts, although it is known that visitor numbers have been gradually increasing on an annual basis. Chatkal has a nature museum which has been visited by around 350 people in both 2009 and 2010. There is no information relating to any accommodation facilities.

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